

A Survey of Influence of Staff's Training and Development Programme on Sustenance of Entrepreneurial Development Training Programme of Ondo State, Nigeria

Erinsakin, Martins Ojo¹ Ph.D; Mrs. Obe, Oyedunni Adebunmi²; Mrs. Agun, Paulinah Olusola¹

¹Department of Continuing Education/Adult and Non-Formal Education,

²Department of Curriculum and Instruction,

^{1,2}Adeyemi College of Education, Ondo, Ondo State, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

The study was carried out on survey of influence of staff's training and development programme on sustenance of Entrepreneurial Development Training Programme (EDTP) of Ondo State, Nigeria. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The study population comprised, personnels of EDTP who had passed through training and development programme, either through the non-system or formal system of education. The sample size of the study was sixty (60) respondents, selected through a snow-balling sampling technique. A self-developed questionnaires by the researchers, entitle "Survey of staff training and development programme on sustenance of entrepreneurial development and training programme of Ondo State, Nigeria" was used to gather data for the study. The instrument was validated by an expert on test and measurement while its reliability was determined through test retest method. 0.68 coefficient reliability was obtained. The research questions formulated for the study were analysed, using descriptive statistics (frequency counts, percentages and means). Based on the results of the study, conclusions were made that staff's training and development programme could enhance peronnel's performance as well as facilitating effective organization and management of EDTP of Ondo State, Nigeria. Based on the conclusions, recommendations were made that the personnel of EDTP of Ondo State, Nigeria should be encouraged by Ondo State Government being a major provider of the programme in the state. Also, Ondo State Government should endeavour to assist on the financial demand of training and development of the personnel of EDTP of Ondo State, Nigeria etc.

KEYWORDS: Staff training, Development, Entrepreneurship programme, Sustenance

Background to the Study

From available reports on organizations and training programmes, staff training and development have been identified as impetus to achieve their objectives. The achievability of organizational productivity is a function of efficient and effective staff training. Akinniyani and Ojo (2008), stated that training is a systematic development of knowledge, skills and attitude needed by organization to carry out jobs assigned to staff. According to Olaniyan and Ojo (2008), training, physically, socially, intellectually and mentally are very essentials in facilitating not only the high level of productivity but also the development of personnel in any organization. Erinsakin (2014), contended that in any organization, human factor is contribute the heartbeat of the organization. Hence, staff's training and development are very germane towards its sustenance. It follows therefore that staff training development are very vital. Hence, through the processes the relevant skills and knowledge would be acquired, thus resulting into making meaningful contributions to overall effectiveness and profitability of organizations.

According to Ajibade (1993), Adeniyi (1995) and Arikewuyo (1999), "training and development is an avenue to acquire more and new knowledge and develop further their skills and technique to function, effectively. Erinsakin (2014), noted that training provides skills, knowledge and aptitudes necessary to undertake required job efficiently, so that workers could have the potentials to work for organization, very well.

The world of work is very dynamic, hence, employers need to be attained with the current trends and changes at the work places. Man is dynamic in nature, the need to be current and relevant in all spheres of human endeavours make staff training and development and, necessary. Chris Obisi (1996), stated that the cardinal aim of staff's training is to enhance competences, which includes; technical, human, conceptual and managerial skills to achieve organizational goals.

Training and development thus become compulsory activities, which any organization must prioritize. This was

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supported by Akinpeju (1999), that staff training and development are continuous processes. "The need to perform one's job efficiently and the need to know how to lead other are sufficient reasons for training and development and the desire to meet organizations objectives of higher productivity, make staff training compulsory. The establishment of Entrepreneurship Development Training Programme (EDTP) by Ondo State Government was principally meant to tackle some socio-economic challenges, besieging the state (poverty, unemployment etc) with their negative consequential effects (Ondo State Government, 2006). Observable, Erinsakin (2016), noted that programme objectives have been militated against by some factors, such as; poor funding, corruption, lack of proper co-ordinating, implementation and monitoring, rarity of facilities etc. Towards providing enduring solutions to these challenges; several researchers had been carried out on the programme. From the extant researchers little or nothing has been done on staff training and development on the programme. Therefore, the study was carried out on survey of influence of staffs' training and development on sustenance of Entrepreneurial Development Training Programme (EDTP) of Ondo State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The implementation of Entrepreneurial Development Training Programme (EDTP) by Ondo State Government, Nigeria was meant among others to tackle poverty and unemployment which were negative consequences effects in Ondo State, Nigeria. One of the major challenges militating against the programme implementation arises from poor acquisition of competencies which, intrinsically are functions of acquiring relevant skills, attitudes and knowledge. It is against this background that this study was carried out.

Objectives of the Study

The general objectives of the study was to carry out a survey of influence of staff's training and development programme on sustenance of entrepreneurial development training programme of Ondo State, Nigeria. specifically, the objectives of the study are to:

1. ascertain whether staff training and development could enhance personnels' performance in EDTP of Ondo State, Nigeria and
2. determine, whether staff's training and development could facilitate effective organization and management of EDTP of Ondo State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

Two research questions were formulated to guide the study;

1. Can staff's training and development enhance personnels' performance in EDTP of Ondo State, Nigeria?
2. Will staff's training and development facilitate effective management and organization of EDTP of Ondo State, Nigeria.

Significance of the Study

The study is significant to all the stakeholders in EDTP of Ondo State Government, Nigeria.

1. The findings of the study will enable Ondo State Government to determine the extent which (EDTP) objectives have been acquired, through staff training and development.

2. The result of the study will serve as an "eye-opener" to staff of EDTP on the importance of the programme on their job productivity and effective service delivery.
3. The study will add to the extant literature, thus, become a source of reference to researchers, who will carry out study within the confine of the study in future etc

Methodology

Descriptive survey research design was used for the study. The study population comprised, of EDTP who had hitherto embarked on training and development, either through non-formal and formal systems. The sample size for the study was sixty (60). A snow balling sampling technique was used. The instrument used to collect data was a self-developed questionnaires by the researchers, entitled "A Survey of Staff Training and Development Programme on Sustenance of Entrepreneurial Development Training Programme of Ondo State, Nigeria". Four likert rating scale of Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Strongly Disagreed (SD) and Disagreed (D). The instrument was validated by an expert in Measurement and Evaluation, while its validity was obtained through test retest method at two weeks interval; using respondents that were not part of the respondents used for the main study. 0.68 coefficient reliability was obtained.

The research questions were analysed using the descriptive statistics (frequency counts, simple percentage and means).

Review of Related Literature

Capacity Building and Organization Development

The United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) (1997) opines that human capacity or development is the process by which individuals, groups, organizations, institutions and societies develop their abilities – both individually and collectively to achieve the set objectives, perform functions, solve problems and to develop the mean and conditions required to enable the process. Therefore, human capacity development hinges on building the inherent potentials of individuals, groups and societies, so as to be more functional and capable of solving problems. UNDP embedded in a sustainable shift in performance and collective behaviour. This process includes, identifying needs, building knowledge, understanding, skills and attitudes that can be implemented through practice and experience of individual that lead to sustainable changes in the collective performance of institutions, sectors, society and the enabling environment.

Further, it was emphasizes that capacity building as a means of promoting sustainable development is a process of initiating and sustaining a process of individual's and organization that can equally refer to change within a state, civil society or the private sector, as well as a change in processes that enhance cooperation between different groups of society. These aspects are emphasized by this definition. They are:

- Capacity building as the catalyst and constant fuel for a process change capacity and
- Involvement of a wide range of different groups in society.
- UNDP (1991) defines, capacity building as the creation of an enabling environment with appropriate policy and legal frameworks, institutional development including; community participation of (woman in particular), human resources development and strengthening of

managerial systems academic and others. UNDP (1991) further stresses, that capacity building is more than training and it includes the following:

- Human resources development, the process of equipping individuals with the understanding, skills, and access to information, knowledge and training that enables them performs effectively.
- Organizational development, the elaboration of management structures, processes and procedures, not only within organisations but also the management of relationships between the different organization sectors (public, private and community). Ann Philbin Capacity Building is a social justice organization. Ford Foundation (1996) defines capacity building as a process of developing and strengthening the skills, instincts, and resources organisations and communities need for survival, adapt and thrive in the fast changing world. Human capacity cuts across all domains. Thus, all sectors need human capacity building. For instance, for organization, capacity may relate to almost any aspect of its work, improved governance, leadership, mission and strategy, administration (including human resources, financial management and legal matters) programmes development and implementation, fund raising and income generation, diversity, partnerships and policy change, marketing, positioning, planning and hosts. For individuals, capacity building may relate to leadership development, advocate skills, training and improving abilities, technical skills, organization skills and other areas of personal and professional development (Linnel, 2003).

Human capacity building is very important and has attracted international attention in recent time, due to the need to face challenges and opportunities brought by globalization and knowledge based economy. Corroborating this, UNEP (2006) expresses, that capacity building has been embedded in the objectives and programmes of work of many international organisations and they offer a wide range of capacity building activities. It can therefore be inferred, that here is an international consensus, that capacity building is a key to promoting sustainable development. It was further stressed, that the ultimate goal of capacity building is to sustain a process of individuals and organizational change and to enable organisations, groups and individuals achieve their developmental objectives. Upon the realization of the place value of human capacity building or development, many national and international partner agencies and organisations have risen to the task of giving financial and

technical supports. The relevance of human capacity developing to this study is that it stressed the development of skills, strength, abilities and potentials of individuals, which programme goals.

Theoretical Framework
Kirkpatrick’s Training Evaluation Model

The trust of Kirkpatrick’s training evaluation model lies on the fact, that evaluation or assessment is the final logical stage in the training process (Kirkpatrick, 2010). This will enable evaluation to be carried out evaluating the effectiveness of training programmes. Kirkpatrick (2010) posits, that if training is to enjoy a high profile, validation of activities is very vital, which he views as two discrete parts of the process, which he describes as internal validation and external validation. Kirkpatrick (2011) maintains that, both levels of validation (internal and external) are closely linked,, functionally.

Internal validation assesses, whether a training activity has achieved its objectives in terms of whether learners of a particular training programme have learnt what they were taught, while external validation aims to find out, if the former trainees have applied, what they have learnt in training to the job context and whether they are to perform to the level expected of them, after training (Kirkpatrick, 2010).

Evaluation becomes very necessary so as to assess the total value of training that is the cost benefits and general outcomes, which benefits the organization, as well as the values of the improved performances of those who have undertaken training. This is the main emphasis of Kirkpatrick’s evaluation model (2010). And its suitability as an evaluative model to this study. Programme of this type. That is skill acquisition and entrepreneurial training model need a thorough evaluation, so as to determine the effect of the training on the participants, behavioural changes that have taken place among the learners, their reactions or feelings to the training and what they can use the training or skill acquired to do.

Kirkpatrick (2010) has come up with an integrated approach to assess the effectiveness of training. His suggest levels within the approach are also in consonance with Stoner, (2002). These levels of approach are presented in the table overleaf with explanation on the levels, aims, when and who method and action.

The table overleaf shows Kirkpatrick’s levels of evaluation model.

Levels	Aims	When done and when by	Methods	action
Reaction	To find out how trainees react to training. This includes, volume and pace, met riding, tutorial style, balance of activities, value of sessions, like and dislikes, admin, points etc.	During training and/or completion of training (Trainer)	Daily reviews, questionnaire completed during or at the end of training. Open forum/course wash up, group monitoring.	“First Aid” treatment to training programme and content
Learning (knowledge and skills)	To find out if trainees have increased their knowledge and/or developed their skills and attitudes as a result of training. Have course objectives been met?	During training or at end of training (Trainer)	Tests, exercise, case studies, oral questioning, etc.	Remedial treatment for individuals. Retraining, reinforcement. Change/review methods.

Behaviour and performance (application of knowledge and skills)	To find out own former trainees have applied their learning job performance. to find out how well training has met their needs/needs of time supervisor	After an internal which allows learning to be put into practice (on average 2-3 months after training) O. (Trainer/Training Manager)	Past questionnaire and/or interviews with former trainees and their managers/supervisors.	Continuous development and updating of training content in response to changing needs, etc.
Organizational outcomes	To find out the extent to which training has improved or influenced organization performance, e.g. reduced costs, improved quality/quantity, increased profit, etc. to assess the cost and value of training.	Periodically, after sufficient time has passed for training outcomes to have had an effect on the function of the organization. (Training Manager/Head of Training)	Past questionnaires and/or interviews with former trainee's departmental managers and other departments who may monitor results, e.g. standard of service, study of company results.	Provide feedback on effectiveness and value of training to the organization. Recommended future pattern of training.
Investment return on training	To assess the cost and value of training. To ascertain what impact training has had on the bottom line.	After a suitable period of time has elapsed in order that, the financial results, i.e. costs and benefits of a training intervention can be assessed (trainer, participants, line manager, accountants, and internal and external experts).	Cost accounting methods and strategies – study company results.	Provide feedback on financial outcomes and implication.

Source: Kirkpatrick Training Evaluation Model (2010)

Each of the levels in table 2.2, succinctly can be put as:

Reaction:

How the trainers and trainees reacted to training, their feelings about the structure and content of the training and the methods employed.

Learning:

The principles, facts and techniques learned by the students

Job/behaviour and performance:

The change in job behaviour and performance resulting from the training or how learning at the previous levels has been applied by students

Organisation:

The tangible results of training in terms of organizational improvement and change

Return on training investments: The cost of designing and implementing training programmes compared to the financial outcomes resulting from such programmes (Kirkpatrick, 2010).

It needs to be stressed, that Kirkpatrick's levels of evaluation model directly reinforces the acquired potentials, abilities, training and resourcefulness in individuals which are capable of increasing the productivity of workers by impacting useful knowledge and skills as stresses (Becker, 1993). Becker (1994) posits, that a connection exists, between investment on workers training and their wages. Thus, Kirkpatrick's evaluation model, taking each of the level with a consideration one after the other will directly bring about development in human training and skills.

Becker (1993) opines, that this can be acquired through non-formal training like, that of skill acquisition and entrepreneurial development training programme this study focused on. Hence, the level of Kirkpatrick's evaluation model is a reinforcement of human capital development. To Kirkpatrick (2010), effects of training on the trainees, reaction, learning, job behavioural and organization and return on training investment must be thoroughly evaluated. This will help determine the extent to which each of the levels aims, methods and hosts have been achieved. This is exactly the point of justification or relevance of Kirkpatrick's evaluation model to this study.

Presentation of Findings and Discussion of Results

Research Question One: Can staff's training and development enhance personnel's performance in EDTP of Ondo State, Nigeria.

Table I: Showing frequency counts, simple percentage and means on can staff's training and development enhance personnel performance in EDTP of Ondo State, Nigeria.

S/N	ITEMS	SD	D	A	SA	Mean	Remarks
1.	The performance of tasks in (EDTP) can enhance through staff training and development	6 (10%)	10 (17%)	12 (20%)	32 (53%)	2.1	Accepted
2.	Staff training and development has no input on enhancement of tasks performance in EDTP of Ondo State, Nigeria	30 (50%)	15 (25%)	7 (12%)	8 (13.3%)	1.8	Rejected
3.	Staff's training and development are continuous basis will bring about achieving EDTP goals of Ondo State, Nigeria	40 (5%)	5 *8.3%)	12 (20%)	40 (67%)	3.4	Accepted
4.	Lack of staff training and development on continuous basis will retard EDTP goals of Ondo State, Nigeria	4 (7%)	6 (10%)	17 (28.3%)	33 (55%)	3.1	Accepted
5.	Staff training and development equips the personnel of EDTP of Ondo State, Nigeria with the necessary skills, attitudes and knowledge for effective service delivery	3 (5%)	4 (7%)	11 (19%)	42 (70%)	3.5	Accepted
6.	Through staff training and development; the personnels of EDTP of Ondo State, Nigeria cannot acquire the needed skills for effective service delivery	30 (50%)	20 (33.3%)	5 (8.3%)	5 (8.3%)	1.7	Rejected
	Total	105 (29.1%)	71 (20%)	53 (15%)	131 (36.3%)	2.7	Accepted

Table 1 above presents the results on can staff's training and development enhance personnels' performance of EDTP of Ondo State, Nigeria. On item (1), 32 (53.3%) of the respondents strongly agreed, 12 (30%) agreed, while 10 (17%) and 6 (10%) disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively.

For item (2), 8 (13.3%) strongly agreed, 7 (12%) agreed, 15 (25%) disagreed while 30 (50%) of the respondents strongly disagreed. Also, in item (3), 40 (67%) strongly agreed, 12 (20%) agreed, 15 (25%) disagreed, while 3 (5%) strongly disagreed. The results of item (4) revealed 33 (55%) for strongly agreed, 17 (28.5%) agreed, 6 (10%) disagreed, while 4 (7%) strongly disagreed.

Besides, on item (5), 42 (70%) of the respondents maintained strongly agreed, 11 (19%) agreed, 4 (7%) disagreed, while 3 (5%) strongly disagreed. Finally, on item (6), 5 (8.3%) of the respondents strongly agreed, 5 (8.3%) agreed, 20 (33.3%) disagreed, while 30 (50%) strongly disagreed.

The table 1 revealed the average mean of ($X = 2.7$) as the total respondents which is greater than the average mean of rating scale of four ($X = 2.5$). This indicates that staff's training and development could enhance personnels' performance of EDTP of Ondo State, Nigeria.

The result is corroborated by Griffin (1978), Ajibade (1998), Adeniyi (1995) and Arikewuyo (1999) opinion that staff training and development is an avenue to acquire competency that would make personnels to functions effectively with an organization. This was also supported by Pitfield (1982), that training provides working the necessary skills, attitudes and knowledge that would boost their productivity.

Research Question Two: Will staff's training and development facilitate effective management and organization of EDTP of Ondo State, Nigeria?

Table II: Showing frequency counts, simple percentages and mean on will staff's training and development facilitate effective measurement and organization of EDTP of Ondo State, Nigeria.

S/N	ITEMS	SD	D	A	SA	Mean	Remarks
1.	Staff training and development will result into effective management of EDTP of Ondo State, Nigeria	4 (7%)	6 (10%)	15 (25%)	35 (58.3%)	3.8	Accepted
2.	Lack of staff training and development can bring about affective management of EDTP of Ondo State, Nigeria	40 (67%)	10 (17%)	3 (5%)	7 (12%)	1.7	Rejected
3.	The best strategy to enhance effective organization of EDTP of Ondo State, Nigeria is through staff's training and development programme	8 (13.3%)	12 (20%)	15 (25%)	25 (42%)	2.9	Accepted
4.	Despite acquisition of skills through staff training and development by the personnels of EDTP of Ondo State, Nigeria, the management of the performance will still be poor	6 10%)	9 (15%)	14 (23.3%)	31 (52%)	3.1	Accepted

5.	The personnels' ability to management EDTP successfully is due to training and development programme which they passed through	8 (13.5%)	10 (17%)	14 (23.3%)	28 (47%)	3.0	Accepted
6.	There is no relationship between staff training and development programme and acquisition of managerial skills	39 (65%)	15 (25%)	7 (12%)	9 (15%)	2.1	Rejected
	Total	105 (29%)	62 (17%)	68 (19%)	135 (40%)	2.6	Accepted

Table 2 shows the result on will staff's training and development facilitate effective management and organization of EDTP of Ondo State, Nigeria. On item (1), 35 (5.8%) of the respondents strongly agreed, 15 (25%) agreed, 6 (10%) disagreed, while 4 (7%) strongly disagreed.

On item (2), 7 (12%) obtained for strongly agreed, 3 (5%) agreed, 10 (7%) disagreed, while 40 (67%) strongly disagreed. Also, on item (8), 25 (42%) obtained for strongly agreed, 15 (25%) agreed, 12 (20%) disagreed, while 8 (13.3%) strongly disagreed. On item (4), 3 (52%) of respondents strongly agreed, 14 (23.3%) agreed, 9 (15%) disagreed, 6 (10%) maintained strongly disagreed.

Besides, 28 (47%), strongly agreed, 14 (23.3%) agreed, 10 (17%) and 8 (13.3%) of the respondent disagreed and strongly agreed, respectively. Finally, 9 (15%) of the respondents strongly agreed, 7 (12%) agreed, 15 (25%) disagreed, while 39 (65%) strongly disagreed. Generally, the result revealed an average mean of rating scale of four ($X = 2.6$) which is greater than the average mean of rating scale of four ($X = 2.5$). Hence, it was concluded that staff's training and development could facilitate effective management and organization of EDTP of Ondo State, Nigeria. The findings was corroborated by Olaniyan and Ojo (2018) submission that training and development are imperative to achieving organizational effectiveness. Further, this was also supported by Erinsakin (2014), that acquisition of managerial skills would enhance overall performance of organization. Hence, through staff training and development the basic management principles and skills could be acquired.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the study it was concluded that staff training and development could enhance staff's ability on tasks performance, as well as; equips staff with the necessary skills for effective organization and management of Entrepreneurial Development Training Programme of Ondo State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made premised on the conclusions of the study;

1. The personnels of EDTP of Ondo State, Nigeria should be encouraged by the state government being the major provider of the programme to embark on training and development programme.
2. The personnel of EDTP should be enlightened on their need for them to undergo training and development programme for their effective service delivery.
3. Ondo State Government should endeavour to assist on the finance the cost of training and developing of the personnel of EDTP of Ondo State, Nigeria.
4. The staff training and development of personnel of EDTP should be a continuous process etc.

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